

Structural defect classification with pre-trained inception network: insights from sample knowledge and model transfer learning through benchmark datasets

J. Prawin*,✉ and Ahmed Umar Murad**

✉ Email: prawinj@serc.res.in

*CSIR – Structural Engineering Research Centre, CSIR Campus, Chennai - 600 113, INDIA.

**Indian Institute of Technology Mandi, Kamand, Himachal Pradesh - 175 075, INDIA.

Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been extensively employed for automatically classifying defects in civil infrastructure from images. The use of pre-trained CNN models is advantageous due to limited training data and their adaptability by fine-tuning for specific tasks or datasets. This paper evaluates the effectiveness of the pre-trained CNN models, Inception ResNetV2, ResNet50 and MobileNet in detecting and classifying structural defects in images of metallic and non-metallic structural components using benchmark datasets: NEU-DET (6 classes), GC10-DET (10 classes), MCDS (6 classes), and BCL (3 classes). The NEU-DET and GC10-DET datasets focus on metallic surface defects, while MCDS and BCL datasets cover non-metallic surface defects (concrete and masonry). Models are trained, validated, and tested individually for each dataset, addressing data imbalance. Performance evaluation studies involves adjusting the last layers during fine-tuning (model transfer) and testing across different datasets (sample knowledge), providing insights into adaptability and generalization. The study finds that the F1-score reaches 99% for NEU-DET, 78% for GC10-DET, 85% for MCDS, and 99% for BCL when tested on the same dataset. However, across datasets with common or similar classes, F1-scores remain above 90% for NEU-DET and GC10-DET but drop to 53% and 76% for MCDS and BCL, respectively, when trained on different datasets. Conversely, F1 scores exceed 90% for all datasets when training data includes all samples of various datasets with similar classes. The results of the study concluded that transfer learning with multiple datasets of similar classes enhances performance and fine-tuning of the last few layers proves sufficient for accuracy within the same dataset and slightly increased fine-tuning enhancing classification across different datasets.

KEYWORDS: Inception network; structural defects; data imbalance; classification;

The integration of automated image-based methods for detecting surface damages is crucial in vision-based structural health monitoring systems and the condition assessment of civil infrastructure. These damages often signify significant degradation within a structure. Researchers have proposed various image-based detection strategies of surface defects using computer vision, image processing methods, and machine and deep learning models.

Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs) have emerged as the most widely DL models for fully automatic image-based defects detection, treating it as

a classification problem. The Deep Convolution Neural Network (DCNN) makes it possible to efficiently and accurately implement image classification, and the accumulated knowledge of DCNN in other domains can be reused for structural defect classification. Training CNN architectures from scratch usually requires a substantial number of annotated images. However, the transfer learning and fine-tuning techniques allow for efficient adaptation of pre-trained architectures, such as those trained on large datasets like ImageNet, to defect classification tasks with limited labelled data. Fine-tuning strategies involve updating specific layers of